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Antimicrobial activity on phytopathogenic bacteria and yeast, cytotoxicity and solubilizing capacity of some deep eutectic solvents (DESs).

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1. Introduction

Deep eutectic solvent (DES) is an eutectic mixture composed of hydrogen bond acceptors (HBAs) and hydrogen bond donors (HBDs) which include a series of individual organic compounds which are solid at room temperature and remain liquid once combined, with a very low melting point [1]. DESs can replace synthetic ion liquids (ILs) with similar physicochemical properties. They are cheaper, easier to prepare, generally safe and less toxic. Both are widely used as solvents for industrial processes such as organic synthesis and extractions [2]. These solvents stand out for their ability to dissolve natural substances as well as enhance the solubility of compounds with poor aqueous solubility [3]. Since co-solvents such as dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) and ethanol are usually used to increase

solubility but have toxic effects, DESs have been investigated for their potential as drug delivery vehicles [1,4]. However, it is necessary to first assess the toxicity and safety of the solvents formed. Choi et al. [5] hypothesized about the presence of these eutectic mixtures in living cells and organisms that allow them to live under extreme environmental conditions such as drought, saline stress, and high and low temperatures. In this case the eutectic solvents include sugars, some amino acids, choline, and simple organic acids normally present in cells as primary metabolites. They are called natural deep eutectic solvent (NADES). These partially explain how nature formulates lipophilic ingredients without the assistance of organic solvents. However, the physiological roles of NADES have a range of unknown functions in nature [6]. Therefore, if such hypothesis is true, it could be thought that these DESs have low toxicity. Paiva et al. [7] have reported that the toxicity of these DESs to the cell lines of fibroblasts are much lower than the imidazolium-based ILs. Radošević et al. [8] have shown that some choline chloride (ChCl)-based DESs exhibit low to moderate toxicity to fish and human cells. However, Hayyan et al. [9] documented that the toxicity to brine shrimp of three phosphonium-based DESs may depend on the composition, viscosity and concentration, with a greater effect on the eutectic mixture than on the individual components. Zhao et al. [10] assessed the antimicrobial activity of DESs on four types of bacteria, two Gram-positive (*Staphylococcus aureus* and *Listeria monocytogenes*) and two Gram-negative (*Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella enteritidis*), showing extremely low toxicity, except for the organic acid-based DES, which inhibited bacterial growth. This is agreement with the results reported by Hayyan et al. [11], who indicated that ChCl-based DESs had no inhibitory effects on two Gram-positive strains (*Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus subtilis*) and two Gram-negative strains (*E.coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*). However, later the same authors reported that all investigated DESs were toxic to some

of these bacteria tested [9]. Also another authors found that choline-containing DESs have a high capacity for attacking *E. coli*, indicating that due to their interaction with bacterial membranes these solvents could be used as antibacterial agents [12]. There are some studies on the cytotoxicity of DESs on yeasts, in which low toxicity of DESs is assessed and correlated with the dehydration effect of the non-toxic agent CaCl_2 [13].

In addition, after examining the toxicity of different DESs on several cell line was found that the toxicity effect of DESs depends on the type of cell line, the combination of components, concentration, molar ratio and the interaction with living organisms, their effect being higher in the mixture than on individual components [14]. There is controversy about the toxicity of DESs to microorganisms and cells, which may be due to the comparison of the results obtained from different and often inadequate methods [15]. One of the objectives of the present study was to determine the biological toxicity of these DES, for which eight phytopathogenic bacteria and seven wine yeasts was examined by obtaining the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) using a broth dilution assay. To the best of our knowledge, there are no previous studies in the literature concerning the toxicity of ChCl-, betaine- and sugar-based DESs to phytopathogenic bacteria. Radosevik et al. [8] and Wen et al. [12] showed that DES could be readily biodegradable would therefore be ideal candidates for use as carriers of antimicrobial substances of natural origin and without adverse effects on human health and the ecosystem.

In addition, the toxicity of DESs to three human cancer cell lines and one healthy cell was analysed using DESs based on ChCl combined with sucrose or xylitol as HBDs, betaine combined with sucrose, and on the combination of sugars - glucose, fructose and sucrose. Furthermore, to measure the solubility of several compounds which are poorly water-

soluble in the presence of nine DESs and to compare their solubility in the conventional solvents ethanol or DMSO was the next objective. The effects of the aqueous dilution of DESs on the solubility of the poorly water soluble flavonoid quercetin was also evaluated. These determinations led to the possible identification of DESs of low toxicity, which could be used as safe carriers of substances or molecules of interest or as cryoprotectors.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Chemicals

Unless otherwise indicated, all chemicals were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (St Louis, MO). Choline chloride (98% purity), sucrose (99% purity), 1, 4-butanediol (99% purity), 1,2- propanediol (99% purity), xylitol (99.9% purity), glucose (99.5% purity), fructose (99.9% purity), betaine (99% purity), levullinic acid (99.9% purity), glycolic acid (99.8% purity), oxalic acid (99.6% purity) and glycerol (99.5% purity). CellROX® Green Reagent (C10444) was purchased from Thermo Fisher Scientific™ (Waltham, MA USA).

2.2. DES preparation

The stability of DES is related to the structure of the compounds and their molar ratio. To use DES in the experiment it is necessary that they are stable and homogeneous at room temperature without precipitation of solid materials over a long period of time. DESs were fundamentally prepared by heating the mixture of three sugars, choline chloride or betaine with different hydrogen donors according to the method described by Dai et al. [1]. Briefly, the components were weighed and mixed together in molar ratio with a calculated amount of water if necessary. The synthesis was carried out in a round-bottom flask, heated in a water bath at 60 °C with continuous agitation for 15-30 min. in a rotary evaporator until the formation of a stable and transparent liquid (Table1).

DESs	Compound 1	Compound 2	Compound 3	Molar ratio	Water %
1	Choline chloride	Sucrose	-	1:2	25
2	Choline chloride	1,4-butanediol	-	1:5	-
3	Choline chloride	Xylitol	-	2:1	11
4	Choline chloride	1,2-propanediol	-	1:1	7.5
5	D(-)-fructose	D-(+)-glucose	Sucrose	1:1:1	22
6	Betaine	Sucrose	-	2:1	13
7	Betaine	Sucrose	-	4:1	16.5
8	D-(+)-fructose	D-(+)-glucose	Sucrose	2:3.6:1	22
9	Betaine	Levunilic acid	-	1:2	-
10	Choline chloride	Glycolic acid	Oxalic acid	1:1.7:0.3	-

Table 1. Composition of DES and molar ratio of components.

2.3. Microorganisms and culture conditions

Bacterial strains *Xanthomonas campestris* (CECT 97), *Erwinia amylovora* (CECT 222), *Erwinia toletana* (CECT 5263), *Clavibacter michiganensis* subsp. *michiganensis* (CECT 790), *Clavibacter michiganensis* subsp. *insidious* (CECT 5042), *Rhizobium radiobacter* (CECT 4119), *Pseudomonas syringae* (CECT 4429), *Pseudomonas savastanoi* (CECT 5019), along with the yeast strains *Saccharomyces paradoxus* (CECT 1939), *Hanseniaspora guillermondi* (CECT11102), *Hanseniaspora uvarum* (CECT 10389), *Metschnikowia pulcherrima* (CECT 12890) and *Torulaspora delbrueckii* (CECT 10589) were obtained from the Spanish Culture Collection, University of Valencia. *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (EC 1118) was obtained from Lallemand (Montreal, QC,

Canada) and *Starmerella bombicola* (CBS 268) was purchased from the Fungal Biodiversity Center, Utrecht, The Netherlands.

2.4. Antimicrobial activity assay

The broth microdilution method was used to determine the toxicity of different solvents against phytopathogenic bacteria and wine yeast. The minimal inhibitory concentration (MIC) was defined as the lowest concentration (mg/L) of the solvent that produced a reduction in the visible growth of microorganisms, according to the National Committee for Clinical Laboratory Standards methodology for bacteria and yeast (NCCLS [16, 17]). The bacterial strains were cultured in Mueller-Hinton broth and the yeast strains in RPMI 1640 for 24-48 h. The microorganisms were suspended in saline solution adjusted to a final concentration per well of 10^6 and 10^5 CFU/mL for bacteria and yeast, respectively. Wells containing 200- μ L dilutions were inoculated with 5 μ L of bacterial or yeast suspension and aerobically incubated at 35 °C for 24 h. The cell concentration of each inoculum was confirmed by count of viable colonies on agar medium using an automated spiral plater (WASP, Don Whitely Scientific Limited, UK) and an automated colony counter (Flash & Go, IUL Instruments, Spain). The pH of the DESs was adjusted with acetic acid to reach an optimum value of 6 for bacterial and yeast in order to avoid the inhibition of the growth of microorganisms caused by inadequate pH values [15]. All solvents were sterilized by filtering through 0.22 μ m filters. Two-fold serial dilutions ranging 75×10^3 to 1200×10^3 mg/L of DES and conventional solvents were prepared in flat-bottom microtiter plates. A positive control broth inoculated with the corresponding microorganism and a negative non-inoculated control broth was included in each microplate. To compare the toxicity of the DES with conventional solvents such as dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO), glycerol, and ethanol, all solvents were tested on each

microplate and a single strain of microorganisms was inoculated. Finally, the microplates were incubated under the same conditions. All experiments were performed in triplicate.

2.5. Cell culture

The human colon adenocarcinoma cell line (Caco-2), the human epithelial adenocarcinoma cell line (HeLa) and human hepatocarcinoma (HepG2) were obtained from the ATCC (#CCL 247 and #CCL 2; Bethesda, MD, USA). Cells were grown at 37 °C with 5% CO₂ and 90% relative humidity in a DMEM or MEM medium (for Caco-2 or HeLa, respectively) supplemented with 10% heat-inactivated fetal bovine serum, 1% non-essential amino acids, 100 U/mL penicillin, and 100 µg/mL streptomycin. The cells were checked for possible mycoplasma contaminations (NeuronBIO Laboratories, <http://neuronbio.com>). For the analysis of the reactive oxygen species (ROS), Caco-2 cells were treated with 50 µM of freshly prepared DES 1 or DES 3 solubilized quercetin for 1 h prior to the addition of 400 µM of tert-butyl hydroperoxide solution (TBH) for 1 h.

Peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) from healthy volunteer with anticoagulant-EDTA were isolated by Ficoll-Histopaque gradient centrifugation. Briefly, 15 mL of blood was layered onto 15 mL the Ficoll-Histopaque in a sterile falcon tube and centrifuged at 800 g for 20 min. The buffer coat layer was collected in a separate falcon tube, washed twice with PBS-AEDT and centrifuged at 300 g for 10 min and the pellet was re-suspended in RPMI media 1640-supplemented bovine serum, 2 mM L-glutamine and 1% penicillin/streptomycin solution and maintained at 5% CO₂, at 37 °C and with 90% relative humidity.

2.6. ROS analysis

The radical scavenging activities of the quercetin diluted in DES 1 and DES 3 were determined using the ROS sensitive reagent CellROX® Green following the manufacturer's instructions. Briefly, after Caco-2 cells were exposed to the distinct treatments (50 μ M for 1 h), a final concentration of 5 μ M CellROX® Green Reagent was added to the cells and incubated for 30 min at 37 °C. Afterwards, the cells were exposed to 100 μ M H₂O₂ and incubated for additional 60 min at 37 °C. Then, the cells were washed with PBS, fixed with 3.7% formaldehyde for 15 min, and the fluorescence signal was analyzed in a Fluoroskan (ThermoLabsystems, MA, USA) equipped with a 485/555 of excitation/emission filters. A control without CellROX® Green Reagent was measured as the auto-fluorescence of the cells. For fluorescent microscopy, the cells were washed with PBS after fixation, exposed to 1 μ g/mL Hoescht 33342, and incubated for 10 min prior to visualization of blue and green fluorescence under a motorized inverted fluorescent microscope Olympus IX81 equipped with a DAPI and FITC filters (Tokyo, Japan). For establishing an appropriate inducer of intracellular ROS in Caco-2 cells, CellROX® Green Reagent was measured by flow cytometry (FACSCanto II, Beckton Dickinson, BD). Mean fluorescent intensity was quantified and analyzed with FACS Diva software (BD).

2.7. Analysis of cytotoxicity by flow cytometry

The cell lines were plated at 400.000 cells/well in 0.5 mL of medium for 24 h. The cells were subsequently exposed to different concentration of DES and DMSO (0.1, 0.5, 1, 5 and 10%) in a 24-well plate and incubated at 37 °C under 5% CO₂ for 48 h. Cytotoxicity was analyzed by flow cytometry as described elsewhere [18]. After incubation, the cells were trypsinized and centrifuged at room temperature, 500g for 5 min. The supernatant was removed and the cell pellet was re-suspended in 1 mL of 1 μ g/mL PI in PBS (pH 7.4)

and incubated for 15 min at 37 °C in the dark. Afterwards, the cells were centrifuged and washed once with PBS (pH 7.4) before analysis. The relative distribution of 10000 events for each sample was analyzed using a Becton Dickinson (Franklin Lakes, USA) FACScanto II flow cytometer with an excitation wavelength of 488 nm and emission wavelength of 568 nm. The data was analyzed using FACSDiva Software (Beckton Dickinson).

2.8. Solubility assay

An excess amount (5 mg) of oleanolic acid, palmitic acid, phenylmethylsulfonyl fluoride (PMSF) camptothecin (CPT) and quercetin were added to 5 mL of each DES or Mili-Q water to obtain supersaturated solutions. The solutions were vortexed for 10 s and then magnetically stirred at room temperature for 30 min at 25 °C. When equilibrium states were achieved, the suspensions were centrifuged at 380 g for 5 min. The supernatant was filtered through a 0.45 µm Millipore filter and 200 µL of the solution were loaded onto a UV-transparent 96-well plate (Corning). A 200 µL sample of each DES was used as blank. The absorbance was measured in a UV-VIS Multiskan Spectrum (Thermo) at 210, 215, and 258 for oleanolic acid, palmitic acid, and phenylmethylsulfonyl fluoride, 320 nm for camptothecin and quercetin, and 350 nm for oil red O. A stock solution (1 mg/mL) of each drug was freshly prepared before use in ethanol (for oleanolic acid, palmitic acid, phenylmethylsulfonyl fluoride, quercetin, and oil red O) or dimethyl sulfoxide (camptothecin). For quantification, nine serial 1:2 dilutions with the appropriate solvent were then prepared to obtain a calibration curve range of 3.9 µg/mL - 1 mg/mL. The R^2 values for the curves were ≈ 1.00 . The solubility of these substances in the different DESs were compared to the solubility of each substance in water and expressed as times the solubility of the drug in water.

Supersaturated solutions of each compound were prepared and subjected to the solubility assay as described above. In addition, serial dilutions (1:2, 1:5, 2:5, 3:5, and 4:5) of each DES in Mili-Q water were prepared.

2.9. Statistical analysis

The data were analyzed using IBM® SPSS® statistics v23.0 for Windows (IBM, Madrid, Spain). All quantitative data are represented as mean \pm SD from triplicate experiments performed in parallel unless otherwise indicated. Mean values among treatment groups were compared by the ANOVA followed by Duncan's multiple comparison test. A level of $p < 0.05$ was accepted as statistically significant.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Antimicrobial activity of DESs

The toxicity of DESs was assessed against eight phytopathogenic bacteria, causing diseases in plants of economic interest, and against seven yeasts present in wine fermentation. The antimicrobial effects of DESs were compared to those produced by conventional solvents such as glycerol, DMSO, and ethanol. Glycerol showed low toxicity to most types of microorganisms and low melting point. Therefore, it is widely used for cryopreservation of fungi and bacteria in concentrations of up to 15%. This solvent is also considered the most effective material for long-term microorganism maintenance. DMSO is used extensively for the dissolution of hydrophobic substances due to its amphipathic nature. It is also cryopreserving but causes cell toxicity at a concentration of 3% [19] However, the toxicity of DMSO is relative and exhibits differences among yeasts, nematodes and human cells. For example, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* suffers from growth defects in 1% DMSO [20]. Ethanol is well known for its highly toxic effects on microorganisms at 3% [21]. Many authors have suggested that

toxic effects of acid-formulated DESs are a consequence of their low pH. In this work, in order to avoid the toxic effects of pH, each of the solvents was adjusted to optimal pH growth of microorganisms. One of the physical characteristics of DESs is its high viscosity, which limits its application in the study of toxicity using diffusion disks. Therefore, MIC experiments involving a liquid medium show better reliability in the results [15]. Tables 2A and 2B show the MIC values obtained for the tested microorganisms. DES composed of three sugars, DES 5 and DES 8, did not inhibit the growth of any bacteria strains and showed a MIC value of 600×10^3 mg/L for most strains,

A)	Bacterial strain	DES 1	DES 3	DES 5	DES 6	DES 7	DES 8	Glycerol	DMSO	Ethanol	
	<i>X. campestris</i> (CECT 97)	150	150	600	150	75	600	79	17	1	
	<i>E.amylovora</i> (CECT 222)	600	300	1200	300	75	600	315	136	12	
	<i>E. toletana</i> (CECT 5263)	600	300	1200	300	150	600	630	136	3	
	<i>C. michiganensis subsp michiganensis</i> (CECT 790)	600	300	600	150	150	600	315	136	6	
	<i>C. michiganensis subsp insidious</i> (CECT 5042)	600	300	600	150	38	600	630	136	25	
	<i>R. radibacter</i> (CECT 4119)	300	150	600	150	75	600	315	136	6	
	<i>Ps. syringae</i> (CECT 4429)	600	150	1200	150	75	600	315	136	12	
	<i>Ps. savastanoi</i> (CECT 5019)	150	150	600	150	75	600	315	136	25	
										6	
B)	Yeast strain	DES 1	DES 2	DES 3	DES 4	DES 5	DES 6	DES 8	Glycerol	DMSO	Ethanol
	<i>S.cerevisiae</i> (EC 1118)	300	300	75	150	600	600	600	315	136	99
	<i>S. paradoxus</i> (CECT 1939)	300	75	150	150	600	600	600	158	136	3
	<i>H. guillermondi</i> (CECT 11102)	300	150	150	150	600	600	600	630	68	25
	<i>H. uvarum</i> (CECT 10389)	600	150	150	150	600	600	600	630	68	25
	<i>M. pulcherrima</i> (CECT 12890)	600	150	300	300	600	600	600	315	68	12
	<i>S. bombicola</i> (CBS 268)	600	150	300	300	600	600	600	315	68	99
	<i>T. delbrueckii</i> (CECT 10589)	600	150	150	150	600	600	600	315	136	3

7 **Table 2.** The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) $\times 10^3$ defined as the lowest concentration (mg/L) to inhibit the growth of phytopathogenic
8 bacteria (A) and wine yeast (B).

9 reaching 1200×10^3 mg/L MIC values for the bacteria *Erwinia* genus and *Ps. syringae*.
10 (Table 2A). These observations indicate that DES 5 and DES 8 were not toxic to these
11 bacterial strains thanks to their composition such as glucose, fructose and sucrose which
12 are used as nutrition sources by these microorganisms [22]. When comparing the toxicity
13 of DESs to DMSO, the results revealed that sugar-based DES 1 and DES 6, and
14 polyalcohol-based DES 3, had lower toxicity than DMSO in all cases. Among them, the
15 least toxic was DES 1, followed by DES 3 and DES 6, with similar MIC values for the
16 different microorganisms except for the bacteria of the *Clavibacter* genus in which DES
17 6 exhibited twice the toxicity of DES 3. The sugar-based DES 7, was the most toxic of
18 DESs tested, with a higher inhibitory effect than DMSO for *E. amylovora*, *C.*
19 *michiganensis subsp. insidiosus*, *R. radiobacter* and the strains of the genus *Pseudomonas*.
20 DES 7 was formulated with the same compounds as DES 6, betaine (HBA) and sucrose
21 (HBD), but with a different molar ratio. DES 7 contains twice the amount of betaine and
22 it appeared to be a determining factor for its toxicity. The results indicated that toxic
23 effects of DESs on bacteria would depend not only on the solvent but on the strain
24 analyzed as well. The sensitivity of a bacterial strain is different within the same genus
25 and even between different subspecies, as occurs with DES 1 against *Pseudomonas*
26 strains and with DES 7 against subspecies of *C. michiganensis*.
27 When comparing the toxicity of DESs with glycerol, the sugar-based DES 5 and DES 8,
28 were the least toxic of all tested DESs for most strains. DES 1 also revealed low toxicity
29 except for *E. toletana* and *Ps. savastanoi*. DES 3, and DES 6 showed greater inhibition
30 than glycerol in the growth of bacteria in most cases analyzed except for *X. campestris*.
31 Therefore, sugar-based DES 1, DES 5, and DES 8 showed low toxicity and stronger
32 capacity to inhibit ice crystal formation similar to glycerol [23], they should be considered
33 candidates for use as safe cryoprotectors.

34 The bacteria analyzed were of the Gram-negative type strains except for the *Clavibacter*
35 genus, which belongs to the Gram-positive microorganisms. Nevertheless, no differences
36 were found regarding the susceptibility of Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria to
37 DESs. Therefore, our results indicated that the toxic effects of DESs depended on its
38 composition as well as on the susceptibility of the bacteria strain.

39 Consequently, we can summarize these results for bacterial strains in an increasing order
40 of toxicity of DESs in the following sequence: DES 5=DES 8 < DES 1 < DES 3 < DES
41 6 < DES 7.

42 Table 2B shows the activity of DESs towards wine yeast strains. The yeasts were less
43 susceptible to DESs than DMSO and glycerol in most cases. Polyalcohol-based DES 3,
44 showed greater toxicity towards *S. cerevisiae* than conventional solvents.

45 Sugar-based DES 5 and DES 8, were found to be less toxic than glycerol, which is logical
46 since glucose, sucrose and fructose are used as nutrition sources by yeast [24]. In addition
47 to its low toxicity, Bufalo et al. [25] reported that sugar-based DESs have the best
48 biocompatibility for reduction reactions catalysed by yeasts. DES 6 with betaine such as
49 HBA revealed the same MIC value of 600×10^3 mg/L as DES 5 and DES 8, and did not
50 show any toxic effect on tested yeasts.

51 The results for yeast strains in increasing order of toxicity of DESs, could be summarized
52 in the following sequence: DES 5 =DES 8 = DES 6 < DES 1 < DES 4 < DES 3 < DES
53 2.

54 3.4. Cytotoxic activities on human culture cell lines

55 The effect of six DESs on cell proliferation in three human cancer cell lines, human
56 colorectal adenocarcinoma (Caco-2) cell line, human epithelial adenocarcinoma (HeLa)

57 cell line, and human hepatocarcinoma (HepG2) cell line was examined by flow
58 cytometry. In addition, the toxicity of these solvents was evaluated on healthy human
59 peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) for comparison. Also in this study, we
60 evaluated the commonly used co-solvent DMSO to increase the solubility of poorly
61 water-soluble compounds to perform biological research and for medical applications
62 [26]. In general, the use of 0.1% DMSO increased the solubility of compounds
63 sufficiently but with certain highly lipophilic compounds, the percentage of DMSO
64 should be increased to 1% or more.

65 Dai et al. [27] studied the integrity of DES in water and concluded that the addition of
66 more of 50% of water affects the structure of DES resulting a solution constituted by the
67 mixture of starting material. Wen et al. [12] and Juneidi et al. [24] reported that the
68 toxicity of DES is reduced with the formation of DES. However, Hayyan et al. [11]
69 showed a higher toxicity for DES than their individual's components. This suggest that
70 HBD have a significance influence at the toxicity profiles. Macario et al. [28] indicated
71 that this difference between toxic effects shows which every mixture can behave
72 synergistically or antagonistically.

73 The half maximal inhibitory concentration (IC_{50}) is a measure of the potency of a
74 substance in inhibiting a specific biological or biochemical function [29]. The results
75 obtained by Mbous et al. [30] concluded that the IC_{50} of pure NADES is in a similar
76 range of their aqueous solutions and significantly lower than aqueous solutions of their
77 individual elements. Atilham et al. [31] showed that to considerate almost independent
78 choline cations, chloride ion and HBD in water solution of up to 97.6 % water content
79 may lead to erroneous prediction of toxicity. The IC_{50} values analyzed for DESs or
80 DMSO, at concentrations expressed in % and μM are collected in Table 3A. The results
81 indicated that the cytotoxicity varied depending on cell lines, but, in general, the solvents

82 studied possessed low to moderate cytotoxicity. To compare the different DESs with
83 DMSO and due to the fact that the molecular weight of DMSO (MW 78 g/mol) is low
84 compared to the average molecular weight of the DESs (on the order to 130 g/mol for
85 DES 3 to 259.5 g/mol for DES 5), it was better to express the IC₅₀ in %. The IC₅₀ of
86 some DESs was similar (orange) or higher (green) than DMSO for all tested cells with
87 the exception of the normal PBMCs, where the IC₅₀ was as high as 5.7%. However, we
88 noticed that DES 8 with three sugars showed more toxicity than DMSO for all cell types.
89 This difference can be explained by the metabolic pathway of each metabolite. Advances
90 glycation end products (AGEs) are modifications of proteins or lipids that become non-
91 enzymatically glycosylated and oxidized after contact with aldose sugars and inflict serious
92 damage to biomolecules increasing ROS production [32]. Bose et al. [33] and Bunn et al.
93 [34] showed that fructose produce at least seven time faster AGEs than glucose. However,
94 for cancer cells, this is complicated by the fact that they require a higher amount of
95 carbohydrates compared to healthy cell for growth which generates an oxidative damage
96 [35]. These findings suggest that the presence of three-sugars (glucose:fructose:sucrose)
97 forms an eutectic mixture in a fixed molar ratio (1:4:2) and are more toxic despite being
98 constituted by sugars. In contrast, these three sugars in a molar proportion of 1:1:1 to form
99 DES 5, showed a higher IC₅₀ value than DMSO for three cancerous cells, being this DES
100 much less toxic. The toxicity of an eutectic solvent is related to various parameters

101

102

		Solvent (%) (μM)							
A)	Cell line	DMSO	DES 1	DES 3	DES 5	DES 6	DES 7	DES 8	103 104
105	Caco-2	3.2 >300	2.2 122	0.9 84	4.1 239	3.4 186	2.7 180	1.4 82	
106	HeLa	2.5 >300	3.3 166	2.7 253	3.2 186	3.2 175	2.0 133	0.7 41	
107	HepG2	2.6 >300	3.2 177	2.3 215	3.5 204	0.8 44	1.8 120	2.1 124	
108	PBMC	5.7 >300	2.3 127	2.8 262	3.5 204	3.4 186	3.8 254	3.0 177	
B)		Selectivity index (SI)							109
		DES 1	DES 3	DES 5	DES 6	DES 7	DES 8		
110	Caco-2	1.05	3.11	0.85	1.00	1.41	2.14		
111	HeLa	0.77	1.04	1.09	1.06	1.90	4.29		
112	HepG2	0.72	1.22	1.00	4.25	2.11	1.43		
113									

114 **Table 3.** IC₅₀ (% and μM in bold letter) of the studied DES with respect to the effect of DMSO on various cells. The colors green, orange and red
115 are IC₅₀ values less than, equal to and greater than DMSO respectively (A). Selectivity index of the DES for cancer cells compared to human
116 peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMC) (B).

117 including density, viscosity, and changes in osmotic pressure that could occur in the
118 medium, not only due to their composition.

119 Also, our data showed that human colon cancer Caco-2 cells were more sensitive to
120 choline-based solvents such as DES 1 and DES 3, than the betaine-based solvents DES 6
121 and DES 7, being DES 1 and DES 3 more toxic than DMSO. DES-3 is constituted by
122 ChCl and xylitol (2:1). Park et al. [36] showed for first time that xylitol inhibits the growth
123 of cancer cells. However, a higher concentration of xylitol was required to inhibit growth
124 of normal cells, suggesting that xylitol is more cytotoxic for cancer cells.

125 Table 3B also demonstrated that, when comparing the effect of DESs in the normal cell
126 PBMCs, to cancer cells, it exhibited significant different cytotoxic sensitivity to DESs.
127 This indicates that tumoral cells are different from healthy cells with regard their cellular
128 membrane. The cellular membrane is composed by a lipid bilayer which acts as first line
129 of defense and it is the first site of interaction. The IC₅₀ values for normal cells were
130 equal or above of those for cancer cells, with the exception of DES 1 for HeLa and HepG2
131 cells or DES 5 for Caco-2 cells that were below. . Therefore, it was found that cell toxicity
132 depended of DES composition and the proportion of its components, as well as the type
133 of cell line. This is agreement with previous reports on the *in vitro* toxicity of ammonium-
134 based DESs [14].

135 These significant differences in IC₅₀ values of the different solvents on normal and
136 cancer cells could reflect an interesting difference in the target sites. The degree of
137 selectivity of a solvent on the different in vitro cell can be expressed by its selectivity
138 index (SI) value:

139
$$\text{Selectivity index (SI)} = \frac{\text{IC}_{50} \text{ of DES in normal cell line}}{\text{IC}_{50} \text{ of DES in cancer cell line}}$$

140 This SI is widely used as a tool for screening the efficacy of possible chemotherapeutic
141 agents. SI values less than 2 indicate general toxicity of tested agent to cells [37]. A SI
142 value greater than 2 means that the agent has more differential activity and is more
143 selective. Based in this, the SI value of DESs under study for each cancer cell line

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164 **Fig. 1.** Viability on tumoral cell line Caco-2 (A), HeLa (B), HepG2 (C) and PMBC cells
165 (D). Values are expressed as mean \pm SD (n=3). One-way ANOVA ($p < 0.05$). Means with
166 asterisk (*) in every line are significantly different respect to DMSO according Duncan
167 test ($p < 0.05$).
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169 are shown in Table 3B. DES 3 exhibited a high degree of cytotoxic selectivity towards
170 Caco-2 cells, whereas DES 6 and DES 7 were selective against HepG2 cells and DES 8
171 against Caco-2 and HeLa cells. These observations are consistent with previous report
172 [14]. However, although the values of SI for some DESs were equal or lower than 1,
173 which may indicate that they represent relatively poor therapeutic candidates, if we
174 consider only the effect of the concentration of solvents at lower doses, below 1% in
175 DESs, the malignant cells were but not the normal cells were clearly affected (Fig. 1).
176 These observations suggest a possible use of DESs as vehicles of low toxicity in healthy
177 cells while causing toxicity in cancer cells according to what was previously reported
178 [11].

179 3.1. Solubility of poorly water-soluble substances

180 Quercetin, CPT, PMSF, oleanolic acid, palmitic acid and oil red O were selected as model
181 substances for the solubility experiments due to their poor aqueous solubility at room
182 temperature. The tested DESs varied in their chemical composition by, utilizing choline
183 chloride and betaine, as HBAs, together with carboxylic acids, alcohols, and sugars, as
184 HBDs, and the mixture of three sugars for which their solubility potentials were
185 evaluated.

186 In order to calculate the solubility advantage of DESs, the ability to solubilize the
187 substances of eutectic solvents was compared to that of the conventional solvents ethanol
188 and DMSO, which are widely used for the solubilization of nutraceutical extracts and the
189 extraction of functional compounds in foods [38,39]

190 The solubility results were expressed as the amount of compound (mg) which is
191 solubilized in 1 mL of 100% DES (Table 4). The maximum concentration obtained for
192 quercetin, PMSF, oleanolic acid, palmitic acid and, oil red O in ethanol and for CPT in
193 DMSO was 0.5 mg/mL. In addition, the solubility of these compounds in water was
194 tested to evaluate the number of folds these compounds are more soluble in DESs than in
195 water. The solubility in water for PMSF, oleanolic acid, palmitic acid and oil red O was
196 negligible; whereas quercetin and CPT showed 0.006 mg/mL and 0.0034 mg/mL,
197 respectively. The solvent DES 10 (organic acid-based), was able to solubilize the
198 maximum amount of quercetin, 0.537 mg/mL, which is not significant difference
199 compared to ethanol and gave the most significant solubility increase by around 8953-
200 fold compared to water. Polyalcohol-based DES 4 also showed the high solubility
201 capacity of quercetin with values of 0.475 mg/mL. Sugar-based DES 1 and DES 6, where
202 the sugar consisted of HBD, and DES 5 and DES 8 formulated with only sugars, showed
203 the lowest solubility capacity. Alcohol-based DES 2 and DES 4 allowed for dissolving
204 CPT at 76% and 87%, respectively, compared to DMSO and increased by 11470- and
205 12794-fold compared to water. For the rest of poorly soluble compounds, solubilizing
206 capacity of DESs was found to be relatively low. For oil red O, palmitic acid, oleanolic
207 acid and PMSF, the maximum values reached were 0.035, 0.052, 0.260 and 0.290 mg/mL,
208 respectively.

209 When comparing these results to those of other authors, differences were found. It should
210 be noted that the solubility values for the different substances in each solvent vary due
211 to factors such as the purity of the compounds, particle size, the analytical method used
212 or the time taken for equilibrium conditions to be reached, as previously indicated
213 Mouden et al.[40]. Previous studies revealed a strong relationship between the structure
214 of the DES components and the efficiency of solubilization of poorly soluble substances.

215 Therefore, this indicated that solubility depended on the type of compounds and
216 formulation of the solvents. DES is formed due to the establishment of strong hydrogen
217 bonding between its components [41]. This hydrogen bonding also occurs between the
218 DES and solutes, with a probable stabilizing effect of solutions of even scarcely soluble
219 compounds, creating a more stable system [42]

220 Our results indicate DES 10 was solvent with the same solubilizing capacity than ethanol
221 and so they could be used as solubility enhancing agents for molecules such as quercetin
222 [43,44].

223 To study the effect of the dilution of DES with water on the solubility of quercetin, DES
224 were classified into three groups (Fig. 2). The first group contained polyalcohols (2, 3 and
225 4), the second one contained sugars (1, 5, 6 and 8) and the third one contained organic
226 acids (9 and 10). It is observed an increase in solubility with the increase in the percentage
227 of DES. Maximum solubilisation was reached with a composition of 60, 80 or 100%
228 DES. Polyalcohol-based DESs have a greater effect on the dissolution of quercetin. DES-
229 4 needed to achieve a 60% concentration to solubilize 0.497 mg/mL of quercetin. It seems
230 that the reason for this high solubility is its structure, in which strong internal interaction
231 OH groups are established and cause interactions with the substances to allow an increase
232 in solubility [45,46]. Similarly, at 60%, DES 10 constituted by acidic components showed
233 similar solubility to DES 4. The maximum solubilization of quercetin was achieved only
234 at 100% in DESs-based on sugars. Thus DES 1, DES 5 or DES 8 were capable to
235 solubilize 0.181, 0.107 and 0.052 mg/mL of quercetin, respectively. However, in DES 6
236 an addition of 20% water increased the solubility to 0.320 mg/mL of quercetin.

237 DESs are very versatile solvents due to their capacity of modulate the solubility of poorly
238 soluble natural compounds, which may be improved by the addition of small amounts of
239 water to decrease viscosity and increase stability. It is assumed that the supra-molecular

240 complex structures of DESs are preserved when the content in water is below 50% while
241 further dilution could produce a solution of the free forms of the individual components
242 in water, showing that gradual changes in the structure of DESs during dilution may affect
243 their physicochemical properties and also their applications [1]. However, Rachmaniah
244 et al. [47] showed that when the percentage of water reached 60% in curcumin extraction,
245 the obtained yield was comparable to 30% of water. Shekaari et al. [41] also demonstrated
246 that DESs diluted with water in an amount greater than 50%, improved the solubility of
247 certain substances, and could be used as co-solvents. DES could have a great potential in
248 drug delivery thanks their dissolving capacity. It is necessary to consider the safety and
249 the toxicity of the components to explore the application of eutectic systems.

DES	Quercetin	Oil Red O	CPT	Palmitic Acid	Oleanolic Acid	PMSF
1	0.181 ± 0.023	0.003± 0.002	0.033± 0.012	MNP	MNP	0.067± 0.022
2	0.309 ± 0.014	0.031± 0.009	0.380± 0.013	0.052± 0.003	0.260± 0.003	0.250± 0.036
3	0.308 ± 0.009	0.003± 0.001	0.054± 0.002	0.029± 0.003	MNP	0.193± 0.013
4	0.475 ± 0.023	0.006± 0.001	0.436± 0.021	0.041± 0.003	0.058± 0.002	0.290± 0.03
5	0.107 ± 0.022	0.003± 0.009	0.043± 0.007	MNP	MNP	MNP
6	0.102 ± 0.064	0.005± 0.001	0.183± 0.035	MNP	MNP	MNP
8	0.052 ± 0.019	0.004± 0.001	0.098± 0.002	0.016± 0.002	0.018± 0.000	MNP
9	0.270 ± 0.072	0.035± 0.003	0.158± 0.032	MNP	MNP	MNP
10	0.537± 0.074	0.005± 0.001	0.228± 0.014	MNP	MNP	MNP

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251 Table 4. Solubility of quercetin oil red O, CPT, palmitic acid, oleanolic acid and PMSF expressed as the amount of compound (mg) that is
252 solubilized in 1 mL of 100% of DES at 25 °C respect to the maximum solubilized in ethanol or DMSO, which was determined for a concentration
253 of 0.5 mg/mL. Values are expressed as mean ± SD (n=3). One-way ANOVA ($p < 0.05$). No significantly different according to the Duncan's test
254 ($p < 0.05$). MNP measurement not possible

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276 Fig. 2. Effect of the dilution of different DES with water on the solubility of quercetin

277 (mg/mL). DES-based polyalcohol (A), DES-based sugar (B) and DES-based organic acid

278 (C). Values are expressed as mean \pm SD (n=3). One-way ANOVA ($p < 0.05$).

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283 3.2. Antioxidant properties of quercetin dissolved in DESs.

284 The antioxidant activity of quercetin in conventional solvents is widely known. In this
285 work, we studied the antioxidant effects of quercetin when it was solubilized in DESs.
286 For this purpose, Caco-2 cells were treated with a dose of quercetin diluted in DES 1,
287 DES 3 and DMSO as control, prior to the addition of TBH, as an inducer of intracellular
288 ROS that were detected by fluorescent microscopy. These DES 1 and 3 were evaluated
289 with a previous cell viability study and presented a better quercetin solubility than DES
290 5, DES 6 and DES 8. DES 2 and 4 were not evaluated for cell toxicity and DES 9 and
291 DES 10 are acidic solvents, so their acidity would impede cell viability.

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293 Fig. 3A shows that the solvents did not increase ROS levels before the addition of TBH.
294 However, when ROS inducer was added, an increase was detected by green fluorescence
295 intensity. The addition and solubilization of quercetin in the different solvents, produced
296 a decrease of ROS due to the oxidation of quercetin. The capacities of DMSO, DES 1 and
297 DES 3 to dissolve quercetin (Q-DMSO, Q-DES 1 and Q-DES 3) were not statistically
298 significantly, and reduced TBH-induced ROS levels by 77, 79 and 82%, respectively (Fig.
299 2B. Therefore, these results illustrated the biological activity of quercetin dissolved in
300 DES 1 and DES 3 by acting as antioxidant in the Caco-2 cell line.

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Fig. 3. Efficiency of DES-solubilized quercetin for preventing the generation of ROS in TBH-stimulated Caco-2 cells. Visualization of ROS level by fluorescent microscopy of cells treated with solvent (DMSO, DES 1, DES 3, TBH and TBH + quercetin solubilized with DMSO (Q-DMSO), DES 1 (Q-DES 1) and DES 3 (Q-DES 3) (A). Quantification of ROS level in cells treated with solvent (DMSO, DES 1, DES 3), TBH and TBH + quercetin solubilized with DMSO (Q-DMSO), DES 1 (Q-DES 1) and DES 3 (Q-DES 3) (B). Values are expressed as mean \pm SD (n=3). One-way ANOVA ($p < 0.05$). No significantly different according to the Duncan's test ($p < 0.05$).

337 4. Conclusions

338 The toxicity of DESs to phytopathogenic bacteria and wine yeasts was assessed in
339 comparison to conventional solvents which are widely used such as glycerol and DMSO,
340 which present low toxicity and are well-known cryoprotector. DESs constituted by
341 sugars, DES 5 and DES 8, showed lower toxicity than conventional solvents for all the
342 yeasts and bacteria analyzed; similar results were obtained with betaine-based DES 6 for
343 yeasts. ChCl-based DES 1 and DES 3 were less toxic than conventional solvents for
344 bacteria. DES 1 also showed very low toxicity for yeasts, followed by other ChCl-based
345 DES such as DES 4 containing alcohols as HBDs. These low toxic DESs have low
346 melting points and highly solubilizing power, to be applied as cryoprotectors with
347 microorganisms and carriers of substances. The rest of eutectic solvents inhibited the
348 growth of microorganisms, with yeasts being less sensitive than bacteria even at lower
349 inoculum concentrations. The more toxic DES was DES 7, that consisting of betaine and
350 sucrose, could be used as antimicrobial against bacteria.

351 The toxicity of DESs towards three cancer cell lines and one healthy cell from humans
352 was studied. The data obtained from IC 50 indicated that the toxicity depends on the DES
353 composition as well as the cell type, but overall, the solvents had low to moderate toxicity.
354 DES 5 is the solvent which presented the lowest toxicity in all cell types that were studied.
355 Therefore, DES 5 could be used in cell cultures. The SI values determined that DES 3
356 exhibits a high degree of cytotoxicity for Caco-2, whereas DES 6 and DES 7 were more
357 selective against HepG2 cells and DES 8 against Caco-2 and HeLa cells. However, if we
358 consider only the effect of the concentration below 1%, malignant cells were more
359 affected than normal cells (PBMCs). DESs showed enormous versatility, which allows
360 us a wide spectrum of use.

361 The solubilizing ability of the DESs formulated with apolar substances has been evaluated
362 compared to conventional solvents. The results showed that DES 10 allowed quercetin to
363 be solubilized as conventional solvents, and that DES 4 was the most solubilizing eutectic
364 solvent for CPT. These high solubilizing DESs were made up of ChCl and an alcohol or
365 acid component such as HBDS, all of which are soluble in water by establishing hydrogen
366 bonds that increase the solubility of solutes and, proving more effective than conventional
367 solvents in dissolving difficult substances to solubilize.
368 Therefore, studies on DESs with other compositions are necessary to increase the
369 amplitude of their utilization for specific applications.in order to prove their affective use
370 as carriers and antimicrobials.

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372 **Compliance with ethical standards**

373 The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest. This article does not contain
374 any studies with human participants or animals performed by authors.

375

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384 **References**

385

386 [1] Y. Dai, J. van Spronsen, G. J. Witkamp, R. Verpoorte, and Y. H. Choi, Natural
387 deep eutectic solvents as new potential media for green technology, *Anal. Chim.*
388 *Acta*, 766 (2013) 61–68.

389 [2] Q. Zhang, K. De Oliveira Vigier, S. Royer, and F. Jérôme, Deep eutectic solvents:
390 Syntheses, properties and applications, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 41 (2012) 7108–7146.

391 [3] E. Rodríguez-Juan, C. Rodríguez-Romero, J. Fernández-Bolaños, M. C. Florido,
392 and A. Garcia-Borrogo, Phenolic compounds from virgin olive oil obtained by
393 natural deep eutectic solvent (NADES): effect of the extraction and recovery
394 conditions, *J. Food Sci. Technol.* 58 (2020) 552-561.

395 [4] H. G. Morrison, C. C. Sun, and S. Neervannan, Characterization of thermal
396 behavior of deep eutectic solvents and their potential as drug solubilization
397 vehicles, *Int. J. Pharm.* 378 (2009) 136–139.

398 [5] Y. H. Choi, J. van Spronsen, Y. Dai, M. Verberne, F. Hollman, I.W.C.E Arends,
399 G.J. Witkamp, R. Verpoorte, Are natural deep eutectic solvents the missing link in
400 understanding cellular metabolism and physiology? *Plant. Physiol.* 156 (2011)
401 1701–1705.

402 [6] Y. Liu, J. Brent Friesen, J.B McAlpine, D.C.Lankin, S.N. Chen, Natural Deep
403 Eutectic Solvents: Properties, Applications, and Perspectives, *J. Nat. Prod.* 81
404 (2018) 679–690.

405 [7] A. Paiva, R. Craveiro, I. Aroso, M. Martins, R. L. Reis, and A. R. C. Duarte,
406 Natural deep eutectic solvents - Solvents for the 21st century, *ACS Sustain. Chem.*
407 *Eng.* 2 (2014) 1063–1071.

408 [8] K. Radošević, M. Cvjetko Bubalo, V. Gaurina Srček, D. Grgas, T. Landeka
409 Dragičević, and R. I. Redovniković, Evaluation of toxicity and biodegradability of

410 choline chloride based deep eutectic solvents, *Ecotoxicol. Environ. Saf.* 112 (2015)
411 46–53.

412 [9] M. Hayyan, M. A. Hashim, M. A. Al-Saadi, A. Hayyan, I. M. AlNashef, and M.
413 E. S. Mirghani, Assessment of cytotoxicity and toxicity for phosphonium-based
414 deep eutectic solvents, *Chemosphere.* 93 (2013) 455–459.

415 [10] B. Y. Zhao, P. Xu, F. X. Yang, H. Wu, M. H. Zong, and W. Y. Lou, Biocompatible
416 Deep Eutectic Solvents Based on Choline Chloride: Characterization and
417 Application to the Extraction of Rutin from *Sophora japonica*, *ACS Sustain. Chem.*
418 *Eng.* 3 (2015) 2746–2755.

419 [11] M. Hayyan, M.A. Hashim, A. Hayyan, M.A. Al-Saadi, I.M. AlNashef, M.E.S.
420 Mirghani, O.K. Saheed, Are deep eutectic solvents benign or toxic? *Chemosphere.*
421 90 (2013) 2193–2195.

422 [12] Q. Wen, J. X. Chen, Y. L. Tang, J. Wang, and Z. Yang, Assessing the toxicity and
423 biodegradability of deep eutectic solvents, *Chemosphere.* 132 (2015) 63–69.

424 [13] F. Cardellini, M. Tiecco, R. Germani, G. Cardinali, L. Corte, L. Roscini, N. Spreti,
425 New zwitterionic deep eutectic solvents from trimethylglycine and carboxylic
426 acids: characterization of their properties and their toxicity. *RSC Adv.* 4 (2014)
427 55990–56002.

428 [14] M. Hayyan, C. Y. Looi, A. Hayyan, W. F. Wong, and M. A. Hashim, In Vitro and
429 in Vivo toxicity profiling of ammonium-based deep eutectic solvents, *PLoS One.*
430 10 (2015) 1–18.

431 [15] J. Torregrosa-Crespo, X. Maset, G. Guillena, D. J. Ramón, and R. María
432 Martínez-Espinosa, New guidelines for testing ‘Deep eutectic solvents’ toxicity
433 and their effects on the environment and living beings, *Sci. Total Environ.* 704
434 (2020) 135382.

- 435 [16] NCCLS, Methods for dilution antimicrobial susceptibility tests for bacteria that
436 grow aerobically. M27-A6, 2003.
- 437 [17] NCCLS, Reference method for broth dilution antifugan susceptibility testing of
438 yeasts:tentative standards. M27-A2, 1995.
- 439 [18] H. Zhao, J. Oczos, P. Janowski, D.Trembecka, J. Dobrucki, Z. Darzynkiewicz,
440 D.Wlodkowic, Rationale for the real-time and dynamic cell death assays using
441 propidium iodide. *Cytometry A*. 77(2010) 399–405.
- 442 [19] S.K. Sharma, R. Kumar, A. Vaishnav, P.K. Sharma, U.B. Singh, A.K. Sharma,
443 Microbial Cultures: Maintenance, Preservation and Registration in: Varma A.,
444 Sharma A.K. (Eds.), *Modern Tools and Techniques to Understand Microbes*,
445 Springer-Verlag GmbH (Switzerland), 2017, pp. 335-367.
- 446 [20] B. D. Gaytán, A. V. Loguinov, V. Y. De La Rosa, J. M. Lerot, and C. D. Vulpe,
447 “Functional genomics indicates yeast requires Golgi/ER transport, chromatin
448 remodeling, and DNA repair for low dose DMSO tolerance, *Front. Genet.* 4 (2013)
449 1–9.
- 450 [21] V. Wadhvani, T. Desai, K. Patel, D. Lawani, D. Bahaley, P. Joshi, P. Kothari,
451 Effect of various solvents on bacterial growth in context of determining MIC of
452 various antimicrobials, *Internet J. Microbiol.* 7 (2012) 1.
- 453 [22] P. M. and P. F. S. Rhodes, *Applied microbial physiology: A practical approach*.
454 London, 1997.
- 455 [23] Y. Qiao, H. L. Cai, X. Yang, Y. Y. Zang, and Z. G. Chen, Effects of natural deep
456 eutectic solvents on lactic acid bacteria viability during cryopreservation, *Appl.*
457 *Microbiol. Biotechnol.* 102 (2018) 5695–5705.
- 458 [24] I. Juneidi, M. Hayyan, O. Mohd Ali, Toxicity profile of choline chloride-based
459 deep eutectic solvents for fungi and *Cyprinus carpio* fish, *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.*

- 460 vol. 23 (2016) 7648–7659.
- 461 [25] S. Bufalo, M.C, Vidovic, S. Redovnikovic I.R, Jovik, Are natural deep eutectic
462 solvents the missing link in understanding cellular metabolism and physiology?,
463 *Plant Physiol.* 156 (2011) 1701–1705.
- 464 [26] N. C. Santos, J. Figueira-Coelho, J. Martins-Silva, C. Saldanha, Multidisciplinary
465 utilization of dimethyl sulfoxide: Pharmacological, cellular, and molecular aspects,
466 *Biochem. Pharmacol.* 65 (2003) 1035–1041.
- 467 [27] Y. Dai, R. Verpoorte, G. Witkamp, Y. H. Choi, The effect of water content on the
468 characteristics of Natural Deep Eutectic Solvents, in *Natural deep eutectic solvents*
469 *and their application in natural product research and development*, The
470 Netherlands, 2013, pp.81-98.
- 471 [28] I. P. E. Macário, S. P. M. Ventura, J. L. Pereira, A. M. M. Gonçalves, J. A. P.
472 Coutinho, F. J. M. Gonçalves, The antagonist and synergist potential of cholinium-
473 based deep eutectic solvents, *Ecotoxicol. Environ. Saf.* 165 (2018) 597–602.
- 474 [29] A. Neubig, R.R., Spedding, M., Kenakin, T., Christopoulos, International Union
475 of Pharmacology Committee on Receptor Nomenclature and Drug Classification.
476 XXXVIII. Update on terms and symbols in quantitative pharmacology, *Pharmacol.*
477 *Rev.* 55 (2003) 597–606.
- 478 [30] Y. P. Mbous, M. Hayyan, W. F. Wong, C. Y. Looi, M. A. Hashim, Unraveling the
479 cytotoxicity and metabolic pathways of binary natural deep eutectic solvent
480 systems, *Sci. Rep.* 7 (2017) 1–14.
- 481 [31] M. Atilhan, L. T. Costa, S. Aparicio, On the behaviour of aqueous solutions of
482 deep eutectic solvents at lipid biomembranes, *J. Mol. Liq.* 247(2017) 116–125.
- 483 [32] N. Shangari, P. J. O’Brien, The cytotoxic mechanism of glyoxal involves oxidative
484 stress, *Biochem. Pharmacol.* 68 (2004) 1433–1442.

- 485 [33] T. Bose, A. S. Chakraborti, Fructose-induced structural and functional
486 modifications of hemoglobin: Implication for oxidative stress in diabetes mellitus,
487 Biochim. Biophys. Acta - Gen. Subj. 1780 (2008) 800–808.
- 488 [34] H. F. Bunn, P. J. Higgins, Reaction of monosaccharides with proteins: Possible
489 evolutionary significance, Science. 213 (1981) 222–224.
- 490 [35] H. A. Liu H, Refined fructose and cancer, Expert Opin. Ther. Targets. 15 (2011)
491 1049–59.
- 492 [36] E. Park, M. H. Park, H. S. Na, J. Chung, Xylitol induces cell death in lung cancer
493 A549 cells by autophagy, Biotechnol. Lett. 37 (2015) 983–990.
- 494 [37] A. Koch, P. Tamez, J. Pezzuto, D. Soejarto, Evaluation of plants used for
495 antimalarial treatment by the Maasai of Kenya, J. Ethnopharmacol. 101 (2005) 95–
496 99.
- 497 [38] G. Davidov-Pardo, D. J. McClements, Nutraceutical delivery systems: Resveratrol
498 encapsulation in grape seed oil nanoemulsions formed by spontaneous
499 emulsification, Food Chem. 167 (2015) 205–212.
- 500 [39] G.P. Zandoná, L. Bagatini, N. Woloszyn, J. de Souza Cardoso, J.F. Hoffmann, L.
501 Schittler Moroni, F. Moro Stefanello, A. Junges, C. Valmor Rombaldi, Extraction
502 and characterization of phytochemical compounds from araçazeiro (*Psidium*
503 *cattleianum*) leaf: Putative antioxidant and antimicrobial properties. Food. Res. Int.
504 137 (2020) 109573.
- 505 [40] S. Mouden, P. G. L. Klinkhamer, Y. H. Choi, K. A. Leiss, Towards eco-friendly
506 crop protection: natural deep eutectic solvents and defensive secondary
507 metabolites, Phytochem. Rev. 16 (2017) 935–951.
- 508 [41] H. Shekaari, M. T. Zafarani-Moattar, A. Shayanfar, M. Mokhtarpour, Effect of
509 choline chloride/ethylene glycol or glycerol as deep eutectic solvents on the

510 solubility and thermodynamic properties of acetaminophen, *J. Mol. Liq.* 249
511 (2018) 1222–1235.

512 [42] E. Rozema, A.D. Van Dam, H.C.M. Sips, R. Verpoorte, O.C Meijer, S. Kooijman,
513 Y.H. Choi, Extending pharmacological dose-response curves for salsalate with
514 natural deep eutectic solvents. *RSC Adv.* 5 (2015) 61398–61401.

515 [43] M. H. Zainal-Abidin, M. Hayyan, G. C. Ngoh, W. F. Wong, C. Y. Looi, Emerging
516 frontiers of deep eutectic solvents in drug discovery and drug delivery systems, *J.*
517 *Control. Release.* 316 (2019) 168–195.

518 [44] S. Emami A. Shayanfar, Deep eutectic solvents for pharmaceutical formulation
519 and drug delivery applications, *Pharm. Dev. Technol.* 25 (2020) 779–796.

520 [45] M. Mokhtarpour, H. Shekaari, F. Martinez, and M. T. Zafarani-Moattar,
521 Performance of local composition models to correlate the aqueous solubility of
522 naproxen in some choline based deep eutectic solvents at $T = (298.15-313.15) \text{ K}$,
523 *Pharm. Sci.* 25 (2019) 244–253.

524 [46] N. López, I. Delso, D. Matute, C. Lafuente, and M. Artal, Characterization of
525 xylitol or citric acid:choline chloride:water mixtures: Structure, thermophysical
526 properties, and quercetin solubility, *Food Chem.* 306 (2020) 125610.

527 [47] O. Rachmaniah, L. Jumiati Fazriyah, N. Hesti Seftiyani, and M. Rachimoellah,
528 Tailoring properties of acidic types of Natural Deep Eutectics Solvents (NADES):
529 Enhanced solubility of curcuminoids from curcuma zeodaria, *MATEC Web Conf.*
530 156(2018) 8–11.

531